

Co-EDTA NPs for the removal of chromium from waste water

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Abstract : Cobalt-ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid nanoparticles (Co-EDTA NPs) are effective adsorbent for the removal of chromium (Cr) from waste water. In this study, Co-EDTA NPs were synthesized by borohydride reduction method, which are then characterized and further used for the removal of Cr. The sizes of the nanoparticles were less than 100 nm. The effects of process parameters such as pH, v/m ratio, contact time and initial concentration on the extent of removal of chromium were investigated to get optimum removal efficiency during adsorption experiment. The effective removal of Cr was observed in the repetitive trials during the removal of Cr.

Keywords : Co-EDTA NPs, borohydride reduction, removal of chromium.

Introduction

One of the most booming fields of science today is nanotechnology and nanomaterials. The properties of nanomaterials significantly alter with decreasing size by virtue of the quantum size effect¹. These properties can be exploited and manipulated for various applications, especially in environmental remediation techniques. Metal chelates like ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) can be used to bind specific heavy metals, these tight-bonding ligands can often mask the toxic effect of heavy metals in liquids². The cobalt nanoparticles (Co NPs) have a rich crystal phase diagram having three nearly isoenergetic structures : face-centered cubic (fcc), hexagonally closed packed (hcp) and epsilon. Recently Co NPs have been synthesized by various methods which include thermal decomposition, gas vapour condensation, hot spraying etc. where sophisticated equipment and rigorous reaction conditions are required and also controlling the size and shape is not possible³. Thus further development of synthetic techniques into practical routes for bulk production of the material rapidly and at low costs requires great inventiveness. In contrast unconventional methods based on chemical synthesis provide an alternative approach for generating nanostructures in terms of material diversity, cost and high volume production.

Rapid growth in industries has led to heavy metal contamination in water sources, in which metals such as

lead, cadmium, zinc and chromium are often released into water. Among them chromium is the chief industrial metal used by different industries. The health hazards associated with Cr is dependent on its oxidation state. Hexavalent Cr can cause liver and kidney damages, liver cancer, dermatitis. National Toxicology Program (NTP) classifies hexavalent Cr into a category having adequate carcinogenic effects through sufficient evidence from carcinogenic tests conducted upon experimental animals. These metals will remain homogeneously distributed within the liquid reaction media. They cannot be neutralized or inactivated. Concentrating or extracting heavy metals can be achieved by using insoluble adsorbents like polymer bound metal chelates⁴, zeolites^{5,6} and natural materials^{7,8}. The present work focuses mainly upon synthesis of Co NPs using EDTA as a chelating agent and to study the capability of Co-EDTA NPs in the removal of chromium from waste water.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1A shows the XRD pattern of the synthesized Co-EDTA NPs. The XRD spectra does not show any characteristic picks indicating the amorphous nature of the Co-EDTA NPs. Figs. 1B and 1C are the SEM images of the synthesized Co-EDTA NPs showing the size distribution within 100 nm. Due to dipole-dipole interactions of individual particles and large surface area the particles are very prone to aggregation. After EDTA chelation

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of synthesized Co-EDTA NPs (A), SEM images of Co-EDTA NPs at different magnifications (B and C).

Co-EDTA NPs remain dispersed in the solution and prevents aggregation of individual NPs causing smaller sizes of NPs and higher surface areas.

The synthesized Co-EDTA NPs are used as adsorbent for the removal of Cr from aqueous solution. Different process parameters such as pH, v/m ratio, contact time and initial concentration are optimized to conduct the adsorption studies. The maximum removal efficiency (95.4%) is found at pH 5 (Fig. 2A), so the pH 5 is main-

tained throughout the experiment during optimization of other process parameters. By adding different amount of synthesized NPs (50 mg to 200 mg) to 100 mg/L Cr solution it is observed that maximum removal efficiency (96.4%) is found at 200 mg of Co-EDTA NPs (Fig. 2B), hence 200 mg of Co-EDTA NPs is maintained throughout the experiment to study other parameters. The time required to reach equilibrium is 8 h (Fig. 2C). As the initial concentration of Cr increased from 100 mg/L to

Fig. 2. Removal efficiency (%) of Cr using Co-EDTA NPs with different parameters. pH (A), v/m ratio (B), contact time (C) and initial concentration of Cr (D).

500 mg/L by keeping the mass of adsorbent (Co-EDTA NPs) constant (as 200 mg), removal efficiency decreased from 100% to 74.8% (Fig. 2D). Hence the adsorbate load is fixed at 100 mg/L of Cr in aqueous solution.

In all cases the removal efficiency (%) is calculated by the $E = (C_0 - C_1) \times 100/C_0$, where E = efficiency of metal removal (%), C_0 = initial concentration of Cr^{VI} (mg/L) and C_1 = final concentration of Cr^{VI} (mg/L).

Langmuir isotherm⁹ which assumes homogeneous distribution of binding sites over the surface of the adsorbent and Freundlich isotherm¹⁰ which assumed surface of adsorbent to be heterogeneous towards adsorbates were checked in the present study. The Langmuir model assumes the formation of monolayer adsorption at constant adsorption energy but the Freundlich model deals with heterogeneous adsorption. Langmuir equation of adsorption isotherm is $1/q = 1/q_{\text{max}} + 1/(b \cdot q_{\text{max}})(C_f)$, where q_{max} and b are the Langmuir constants. The plot of $1/q$ vs $1/C_f$ is linear and q_{max} is determined from slope of the line whereas b is calculated from intercept. Constant b which is related to the energy of adsorption through the Arrhenius equation estimates the affinity of the sorbent to the metal ions. q_{max} predicts the total number of binding

using the Freundlich equation of adsorption isotherm as $\log q = \log K + (1/n) \log C_f$ where q is the metal ion sorbed (mg/g), C_f is the equilibrium concentration of metal ion in solution in mg/L, K and n are Freundlich constants. K is a measure of the degree or strength of adsorption and the value of K is proportional to absorption while $1/n$ is used as an indication of isocratic absorption (at $1/n = 1$) or decreases with increasing metal ions concentrations (with $1/n \neq 1$)¹². The constants K and $1/n$ were determined from slopes and intercepts of the plot between $\log q$ and $\log C_f$.

All the experiments are done in duplicates to confirm the accuracy. Adsorption of Cr on Co-EDTA NPs is found to follow both Langmuir adsorption isotherm and Freundlich adsorption isotherm with R^2 greater than 0.95 (Fig. 3). Further the synthesized Co-EDTA NPs can be used twice effectively with the same initial concentration of Cr but after two times the removal efficiency decreases to less than 40 percent.

Experimental

Reagents :

Synthesis of Co-EDTA nanoparticles : The Co-EDTA

Fig. 3. Adsorption isotherms-Langmuir adsorption isotherm (A) and Freundlich adsorption isotherm (B).

sites that are available for sorption and q quantifies the number of binding sites that are occupied already by the metal ions at the concentration of C_f ¹¹.

Adsorption-partition constants are determined for metal

NPs were prepared by borohydride reduction method. Here all the solutions were maintained below 10 °C. 3.7 g of cobalt acetate (0.01 N) was dissolved in 150 ml of 30% ethanol, then 100 ml of 0.2 N EDTA in distilled

water was added for chelation. The solution was stirred well using Teflon blade connected to propeller (SS316) after complete chelation and 100 ml of 0.5 N sodium borohydride was added for reduction with the help of pressure equalizer funnel. The flask was kept for stirring at 500 rpm for 10 min using the propeller. After complete reduction the solution was allowed to stand for 20 min in the flask for settling of Co-EDTA NPs formed. Then this solution was centrifuged and the residue was washed thrice using ethanol (99.9%). Then the Co-EDTA NPs were dried at room temperature, pulverized and stored at room temperature.

Characterization of NPs :

The morphology and size of solid Co-EDTA NPs were characterized using powder XRD, SEM after sprinkling the solid samples on the adhesive metallic disk supported carbon tape. Powder XRD analysis was carried out with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$). XRD pattern of Co-EDTA nanoparticles was recorded over a 2θ range of 10–90°. Concentration of chromium content during removal studies was quantified using Atomic Adsorption Spectroscopy (AA240, Varian, Australia).

Removal of Cr by Co-EDTA nanoparticles :

Effect of pH on removal efficiency : In order to study the effect of pH, 20 ml of 100 mg/L Cr solution was taken into four different reaction tubes and the pH was adjusted to 3, 4, 5 and 6 respectively. 100 mg of Co-EDTA NPs were added to each bottle and kept for spinning at 50 rpm for 4 h in a rotospin. After spinning, the solution was filtered and then concentration of Cr was estimated in the filtrate by AAS.

Effect of v/m ratio on removal efficiency : 20 ml of Cr solution (100 mg/L) was taken into four different reaction tubes and the pH was adjusted to 5. Varying amount of Co-EDTA NPs i.e. 100, 150, 200 and 250 mg were added. Then the bottles were spinned at 50 rpm for 4 h, then solutions were filtered and AAS analysis was carried out. Highest removal efficiency was obtained at v/m ratio of 100 (200 mg of Co-EDTA NPs in 20 mL). There was a decreasing trend in efficiency with increasing v/m ratio.

Effect of contact time in removal of Cr : 20 ml of Cr solution (100 mg/L) was taken into five different reaction tubes and the pH was adjusted to 5 in each one of them.

Then 200 mg of Co-EDTA NPs were added to each bottle. The bottles were kept for spinning at 50 rpm for 2, 4, 8, 18 and 24 h, then solutions were filtered and AAS analysis was carried out.

Effect of initial concentration on removal efficiency : 100, 200, 400 and 600 mg/L of the Cr solutions were prepared and from which 20 ml of each solution was taken into four different reagent bottles and the pH was adjusted to 5. 200 mg of Co-EDTA NPs were added to each bottle. Then these bottles were kept for spinning at 50 rpm for 10 h, then solutions were filtered and subjected to AAS.

Conclusion

Co-EDTA NPs were synthesized by borohydride reduction method. The particles were found to be air stable at room temperature without undergoing any oxidation. XRD results show that the Co-EDTA NPs were amorphous in nature. Further Co-EDTA NPs acted as an adsorbent in remediation of Cr^{VI} and maximum removal was at pH 5. This indicates the potential application of the Co-EDTA NPs in removal of Cr^{VI} from industrial effluents. By studying the kinetics it was found that the reaction mixture reached equilibrium by 8 h. It was also found that with the increasing concentrations of Cr^{VI} in the solution, there was a decrease in the removal efficiency of Co-EDTA NPs. To conclude the synthesized Co-EDTA NPs can be effectively used to remove Cr^{VI} from waste water.

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